

Let's care

BUILDING SAFE AND CARING SCHOOLS
TO FOSTER EDUCATIONAL INCLUSION
AND SCHOOL ACHIEVEMENT

D7.3 Quality Management Plan - Review and Update

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe research and innovation programme
project number 101059425

Funded by the European Union under grant agreement of the project 101059425. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

DELIVERABLE ID

Deliverable No.	D7.3	Work Package No.	WP7	Task/s No.	Task 7.1
Work Package Title	PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND LEGAL AND ETHICAL CHALLENGES				
Linked Task/s Title	ADMINISTRATIVE AND FINANCIAL COORDINATION				
Dissemination level	PU	<i>(PU-Public, SEN-Sensitive)</i>			
Due date deliverable	2024-09-30	Submission date	2024-09-30		
Deliverable name	QUALITY MANAGEMENT PLAN – REVIEW AND UPDATE				

DOCUMENT CONTRIBUTORS

Deliverable responsible	COMILLAS	
Contributors	Organisation	
MERCEDES FERNÁNDEZ	COMILLAS	
ANA BERÁSTEGUI	COMILLAS	
ISABEL MUÑOZ	COMILLAS	
OLATZ MIRANDA	ZIC	
CAROLINA SIMÓN	ZIC	
Reviewers	Organisation	
EVA BAJO MARCOS	COMILLAS	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Comments
0.1	2024-08-26	First draft ready for review
0.2	2024-09-05	Second draft including external revision
1.0	2024-09-27	Final version ready for submission

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1. Purpose	8
1.2. Relation to other project documents.....	8
2. Project basis.....	8
2.1. Participants	8
2.2. Contractual documents.....	9
2.2.1. Grant Agreement (GA).....	10
2.2.2. Grant Agreement Amendments	10
2.2.3. Consortium Agreement (CA).....	11
3. Project Structure	11
3.1. Work packages list/overview	12
3.2. Overall work breakdown structure	12
3.3. Project duration, budget and EC Contribution	13
4. Project reporting	13
4.1. Periodic Reports.....	13
4.1.1. Time limit for reporting	13
4.1.2. Content of periodic reports	14
4.1.3. Periodic Reporting workflow and submission procedure	15
4.2. Continuous reporting.....	15
4.2.1. Deliverables	16
4.2.2. Submission of Deliverables.....	17
4.2.3. Progress reporting	17
4.3. Report on the distribution of the financial contribution between beneficiaries	17
4.4. Financial Information – Reporting costs	18
4.4.1. Eligible costs-Non eligible costs.....	18
4.4.2. Details about the nature of costs to submit	18

4.4.3.	Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS)	18
4.4.4.	Financial documentation to be kept- supporting documents of costs claimed	19
5.	Project Management	19
5.1.	Governance Structure	19
5.2.	Risk management.....	19
5.3.	Quality management plan.....	20
6.	Work Information Management	21
6.1.	Quality Planning	21
6.1.1.	Meetings	21
6.1.2.	Periodic reporting	21
6.1.3.	Performance indicators reporting	22
6.1.4.	Decision making mechanism	22
6.1.5.	Veto rights.....	22
6.2.	Quality Control and monitoring	23
6.2.1.	Document management and internal communication	23
6.2.2.	Technical information Flow Chart.....	23
6.2.3.	Administrative Information Flow.....	23
6.2.4.	Templates	24
6.2.5.	Review and submission of deliverables.....	24
7.	Financial Contributions and payment issues.....	24
8.	Project Changes and Potential problem areas	25
8.1.	Project Changes: Amendments to the GA and / or Communication letters to the EC.....	25
8.1.1.	Changes requiring amendment to the Grant Agreement	25
8.1.2.	Changes which do not require an amendment: information procedure	26
8.1.3.	How do I request an amendment?	26
8.2.	Potential Problem Areas	28

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
AE	Affiliated Entity
AP	Associated Partner
CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEB	External Ethics Board
GA	Grant Agreement
GenA	General Assembly
IFS	Individual Financial Statement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MoM	Minutes of Meetings
PC	Project Coordinator
PFSIGN	Project Financial Signatory
PM	Person Month
PMAB	Policy Makers Advisory Board
PO	Project Office
RP	Reporting Period
TC	Technical Committee
QMP	Quality Management Plan
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The Quality Management Plan (QMP) is a comprehensive document that provides essential information for the effective monitoring of project quality from initial planning through to final delivery. It sets out the project's quality policies, procedures, criteria, and scope, and defines roles, responsibilities, and authorities. The Quality Management Plan is an integral part of the project's management. It is intended for the use of the Consortium partner for the effective execution of the project.

The Deliverable D7.1 – Quality Management Plan is a document of internal use within LET'S CARE Consortium, designated as "SENSITIVE" regarding the dissemination level, and which purpose is to provide a quick overview concerning the most relevant managerial aspects of the project.

The current deliverable D7.3 Quality Management Plan – review and updated is an updated version of the D7.1. Since it is designated as "PUBLIC" regarding the dissemination level, sensitive information has been removed, but a complete version is available for the consortium. Given the nature of this document, this deliverable is alive and can be modified according to the project needs.

This deliverable has been prepared by COMILLAS and ZIC with the contribution of partners and based on internal procedures and templates set by ZIC. This deliverable has also been supported on the Consortium Agreement (CA) document, updated because of IPA's partner termination.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose

The aim of the LET'S CARE Quality Management Plan is to give a quick overview of the most relevant managerial aspects of the project, setting the rules and responsibilities of the partners aimed at ensuring a good quality and progress of the work.

This document summarises all the required knowledge for the good management of the project and contains all information related to the management strategy, structure of the consortium, reporting issues, templates to be used, publication procedures, etc. Furthermore, the purpose of this guide is to clarify legal and financial aspects of the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) that may need further clarifications to beneficiaries.

This guide is alive and can be modified according to the project needs including relevant issues and changes in the project or procedures. Each time the document is updated, all partners will be duly informed about the updates and the changes made with respect to the previous version.

1.2. Relation to other project documents

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Management Plan is overruled by GA including its Annexes or latest Amendment in force and the CA with its possible addenda(s).

2. Project basis

2.1. Participants

The list of Project Beneficiaries is included in the GA/latest Amendment and in the CA. By the time of preparing this document, these are:

Table 1. List of Project Beneficiaries

N.	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
1	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	COM	Spain
2	CIDALIA CONSULTORIA TECNICA EN DIVERSIDAD SLL	CID	Spain

3	FACHHOCHSCHULE VORARLBERG GMBH	FHC	Austria
4	ISTITUTO COMPRENSIVO DI BOSCOCHIESANUOVA	POLO	Italy
5	FUNDACION PROMAESTRO	PROMA	Spain
6	TIME.LEX	TLX	Belgium
7	CONSEJERIA DE EDUCACIÓN Y EMPLEO - JUNTA DE EXTREMADURA	JEX	Spain
8	STOWARZYSZENIE ARID	ARID	Poland
9	PANEVEZIO RAJONO SVIETIMO CENTRAS	PRSC	Lithuania
10	ZABALA INNOVATION CONSULTING, S.A.	ZIC	Spain
11	UNIVERSIDADE CATOLICA PORTUGUESA	UCP	Portugal
12	UNIWERSYTET IGNATIANUM W KRAKOWIE	UIK	Poland
13	STICHTING INTERNATIONAL PARENTS ALLIANCE- Terminated 30 June 2024	IPA	Netherlands
14	KITE	KITE	Bulgaria

A contact list per organisation will be available on the LET'S CARE web and repository at all times.

New contacts or changes/corrections to the contacts should be sent to:

[SENSITIVE]

2.2. Contractual documents

The reference documents for the project Consortium members, which define the tasks, rights and obligations of the partners are the GA (including its annexes) or latest Amendment in force (if any) and the CA (including its addenda if any). Both documents will be accessible through the LET'S CARE repository.

2.2.1. Grant Agreement (GA)

Grant Agreement with the EC: GA No. 101059425. This is the contractual document signed by all the project partnership which defines the rights and obligations of the Consortium regarding the EC. The GA includes the following annexes:

- Annex 1 Description of the action (DoA): This is the contractual document which describes the work to be performed by the project Consortium.
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action.
- Annex 3 Accession Form: This is the form signed by all partners and the Project Coordinator (PC) to access the GA, as identified in Article 40.1 of the GA.
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements. To be used for the periodic financial reporting to the EC.
- Annex 5 Specific rules.

The project GA will be available for all partners in the LET'S CARE repository.

2.2.2. Grant Agreement Amendments

An amendment to a GA is a legal act modifying the commitments stated in the GA and which may create new rights or impose new obligations on the parties. It allows the Consortium to modify the GA during the project lifetime.

An amendment can be requested either by the EC to the consortium or by the consortium to the EC. The amendment enters into effect through an exchange of letters:

- Case 1: the consortium formulates the amendment to the EC: a letter-request from the PC on behalf of the consortium.
- Case 2: the amendment is formulated by the EC to the consortium: a letter of acceptance of the amendment (the PC on behalf of the consortium).

Amendments can only be done by the PC who, after launching the amendment request, and once all the amendment data are completed, signs electronically the request. The procedure for requesting an amendment is described with further detail in the Section 8.1.3.

Any project amendment submitted by the consortium is subjected to official acceptance by the EC. Any substantial modification to the content of Annex 1 (DoA), as well to the administrative information of the project (related to project partners, project budget, etc.) needs the official acceptance of the EC through an amendment process.

The project coordination team strongly recommends the partners to check with the PC any issue that might be subject to an amendment.

For more detailed information about Project Changes (amendments to the GA), see Section 8.1.

A first Amendment was requested in June 2023 and approved by July 2023 concerning the following changes:

- Change of Annex 1
- Change of the project name
- Change of the project acronym
- Change of Annex 2
- Change of the maximum grant amount (Annex 2)

Furthermore, a second Amendment is being requested requested in September 2024 concerning the following changes:

- Change of Annex 1
- Beneficiary Termination (IPA)
- Change of Annex 2

2.2.3. Consortium Agreement (CA)

The Consortium Agreement is the internal contract of the consortium partners which is signed and is accepted by all partners. It defines the Consortium internal rules for project management as well as the Consortium organization and decision taking mechanisms. In case of discrepancy, the CA is overruled by the GA.

The project CA will be available for all partners in the LET'S CARE repository, accessible for all partners. The CA is being updated as in order to adapt it to the new Consortium after the exit of IPA on June 30, 2024.

3. Project Structure

The overall plan of the project follows the tasks and activities, schedule and budget as laid down in the DoA (Annex 1 to the GA). The guiding point of all work and planning will be the Deliverables due to the EC along the 3 Reporting Periods (RP) of LET'S CARE.

3.1. Work packages list/overview

LET'S CARE is a 48-month project organized in the following Work Packages:

[SENSITIVE]

The Work Packages structure and a WP relation, as defined in the DoA, are shown in Figure 1: The detailed description of each Work Package's work is described in Annex I of the GA – (DoA).

Each Work Package (WP) has designated a WP Leader that is the partner in charge of the leadership and coordination of the technical and economic aspects of the WP. This includes responsibility for the preparation of any technical reports, achieving milestones, achieving deliverables, provision of deliverables to the PC on schedule, and provision of interim and progress reports to the PC on schedule. The partners concerned shall appoint a named individual to carry out the role of WP Leader. Partners responsible for these deliverables must be cautious with the submission of these deliverables.

[SENSITIVE]

3.2. Overall work breakdown structure

A work breakdown structure has been defined by all partners to establish the main roles and responsibilities within the Work Plan. The scope of this structure corresponds to a subtask level of detail where applicable. It is needed to emphasize that specific temporary changes/deviations (duration, due dates, etc.) have affected to the current design of the work plan related to tasks, subtasks, deliverables or milestones. In this sense, they are being analysed, justified, and then approved by all partners with the consensus from the EC for their future implementation. On the other hand, those deviations considered as "major changes" by the EC have been treated in accordance with the principles included in the GA and required their introduction in previous amendments processes already finished.

The partners involved in each Work Package and the breakdown of the effort per participant in each Work Package can be found in the Annex 1 – DoA Part A of the GA, within "List of work packages" and "Staff effort" sections respectively.

The timing of the different WPs is shown below, updated in line with the Amendment that is under preparation by the time of submitting this deliverable:

[SENSITIVE]

3.3. Project duration, budget and EC Contribution

The effective start of the project is 01.10.2022, and the project ends 48 months later, on 31.09.2026. The project has an overall budget of 2,953,671.88€, of which a maximum of 2,953,668.25€ shall be financed by the European Commission (EC).

The budget detailed per beneficiary and the corresponding EU contribution of each beneficiary is detailed in the Annex 2 to the Grant Agreement – Description of Action (DoA). In addition, in the Annex 2 - Estimated Budget for the action - is also detailed by cost activities.

The EC contribution to each of the beneficiaries is a maximum contribution conditioned to the acceptance by the EC of expenses up to the budget of the partner (this means that if a partner spends less than what it is shown in its approved budget -or the Commission does not accept all its costs-, it will receive only the proportional part of the EC contribution).

4. Project reporting

The project reporting is the procedure used by the EC to assess and follow up the EU funded projects. It is compulsory to EC and the project continuity depends on these reports.

It is important to remark that project reporting is a responsibility of the whole Consortium and every partner has to be involved in it. The project coordinator is responsible for gathering the information and reports from the different partners and consolidating it before sending it to the EC.

Additionally, one interim progress report will be prepared and submitted to the EC as deliverable to cover project progress (more detailed information in section 4.1.3).

4.1. Periodic Reports

LET'S CARE project is divided into 3 RPs of the following duration:

- RP1: from month 1 to month 12: from 01/10/2022 to 30/09/2023
- RP2: from month 13 to month 27: from 01/10/2023 to 31/12/2024
- RP3: from month 28 to month 48: from 01/01/2025 to 30/09/2026

4.1.1. Time limit for reporting

All the periodic reports (including the final report) shall be submitted by the PC within 60 days after the end of the reporting period to the EC. According to this, the deadlines for submitting the above-mentioned periodic reports to the EC are the following:

- RP1 periodic report deadline: 30/11/2023
- RP2 periodic report deadline: 28/02/2025
- RP3 periodic report deadline: 30/11/2026

At the end of each reporting period, the EC shall evaluate and approve project reports and deliverables and disburse the corresponding payments within 90 days of their receipt. Payment is subject to approval of the reports by the EC. In the case that the EC requests any further information, clarification or documentation on the periodic report, the time of 90 days will be stopped from the EC side restarting the count-down upon reception of requested information.

4.1.2. Content of periodic reports

The content of the Periodic reports is compulsory and determined by the EC in accordance to Article 21.2 of the GA. A template of the Periodic report will be available at LET’S CARE repository. It can also be downloaded from the following link: [periodic-report horizon-auratom en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/periodic-report-horizon-auratom-en.pdf)

The structure of the Periodic Report contains the technical and financial report and it is shown in the table below:

Table 2- Structure of the periodic reports

PERIODIC TECHNICAL REPORT	PERIODIC FINANCIAL REPORT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Part A: Contains structured tables with project information ● Part B: Narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Individual financial statements (IFS) (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary; ● Summary financial statement ● Certificate on the financial statements (CFS) (if threshold is reached and only in the last periodic report)

Part A of the Periodic Technical Reporting is generated by the IT system of the Funding & Tenders portal. It is based on the information entered through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules (see section 4.2 for more information concerning continuous reporting) of the electronic exchange system in the Participant Portal. The PC will be the responsible of entering such information, which will be able to be updated in the continuous reporting module at any time during the life of the project.

Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document following the template of Part B Periodic Technical report. This will also be done by the PC.

The IFS as well as the explanations of the Use of Resources corresponding to each partner (and linked third parties) requesting an EU contribution will be completed on-line by each beneficiary. Beneficiaries will complete their financial statement (and that of their affiliated entities, if applicable). See section 4.1.3 for further detail.

4.1.3. Periodic Reporting workflow and submission procedure

DATA COLLECTION FROM BENEFICIARIES AND ROLES

For the preparation of the periodic reports, technical and financial inputs are necessary from beneficiaries. In order to ensure the accomplishment of the periodic reporting deadlines, a reporting workflow has been defined:

[SENSITIVE]

INDIVIDUAL FINANCIAL STATEMENT (IFS) COMPLETION

IFS COMPLETION WORKFLOW:

The timely receipt of the cost statement duly filled out is of primary importance for reporting issues as well as for providing a proper explanation of the use of the resources within the period in accordance with the EC requirements.

To support this process, a Cost Statement template will be created and delivered to every beneficiary. The cost statement is aimed at collecting from all partners costs incurred in the period and the explanation of the use of the resources required by the EC in the periodic report. Costs shall be detailed at WP level.

Costs declared must be set out in Annex 2 (Estimated budget for the action). Costs not foreseen might be reported and claimed but they will have to be duly explained if we expect that the EC would accept them.

The following rules shall be followed for the financial report of the LET'S CARE project:

[SENSITIVE]

4.2. Continuous reporting

In addition to the project reporting obligations, the EC activates a Continuous reporting module via the Funding & Tenders portal at the time the project starts.

This module makes available the electronic submission of Deliverables plus Periodic Reporting information that can be optionally entered at any time during the life of the project such as:

- Project summary
- Researchers involved in the project
- Submit deliverables
- Report progress in achieving milestones
- Follow up critical risks
- Results
- Standards
- Patents
- Datasets
- Information about dissemination & communication issues:
 - Publications
 - Dissemination activities
 - Communication activities
- Beneficiaries feedback
- Impact
- Other results

The PC will be responsible for completing the continuous reporting via Funding and Tenders Portal with the inputs provided from the required partners.

4.2.1. Deliverables

Each WP will have a number of associated deliverables. It is key for the successful implementation of LET'S CARE that all deliverables are rigorously monitored throughout the course of the project. In this regard, ZIC will send periodic reminders to the involved partners 5 weeks before the deadline.

The list of deliverables for the 48 months of the project is shown in the table below. It is shown in chronological order, to facilitate the follow up of deliverable submission. If a deliverable is comprised of several versions to be submitted in different dates, the deliverable is shown as many times as dates, with the indication of the release month (month #).

Partners responsible for these deliverables must be cautious with the submission of these deliverables:

[SENSITIVE]

4.2.2. *Submission of Deliverables*

During the course of the Project, the deliverables identified in Annex 1 to the GA have to be finished and submitted to the EC according to the timetable specified in the Deliverable list. All deliverables have to be submitted electronically to the EC through the Funding & Tenders portal Portal. The PC will be the person responsible for uploading the final version of the deliverable in the Funding & Tenders portal and submit it electronically to the EC.

In case any kind of delay is detected, this should be reported by the Lead Beneficiary to the PC, so the necessary corrective actions are made and the EC officer is kept informed in advance.

4.2.3. *Progress reporting*

The progress reporting aims to ensure the correct progress of the project tasks at the middle point of a reporting period.

Each partner and WP leader will report project progress to the PC according to this:

- **D7.4 - Interim progress report (M27-M36)** -- Due date M36

The deliverable will *cover technical progress, results, deliverables and compliance with the WP schedule, as well as the monitoring and updating of the identified risks*. Progress of the tasks will report deviations from agreed time scales and corrective actions.

The template of the interim progress report will be available in the project repository.

4.3. **Report on the distribution of the financial contribution between beneficiaries**

The PC must distribute the amounts received to the beneficiaries — without unjustified delay (Article 22.1 of GA).

The Commission/Agency will be informed of the distribution of the payments by the PC in the event of recovery at the payment of the balance (see Article 22.2). In this case, there will be a request to the PC in order to submit a report on the distribution of payments to the beneficiaries within 30 days of receiving notification.

If the participation of one or more beneficiary is terminated (see Article 32 of GA), the PC will submit to the beneficiary concerned, within 30 days from when termination takes effect a report on the distribution of payments to the beneficiary concerned.

4.4. Financial Information – Reporting costs

The financial reporting, including both in the Periodic and the Final Reporting, must take into account the criteria for cost eligibility.

4.4.1. Eligible costs-Non eligible costs

Contractors should report the costs incurred by using the Horizon Europe eligible costs which are structured as follows according to Article 6 in the GA:

Direct costs:

- Personnel costs (Article 6.2A)
- Direct costs of subcontracting (Article 6.2B)
- Purchase costs (Article 6.2C):
 - Travel and subsistence
 - Equipment
 - Other goods, works and services
- Other cost categories (Article 6.2D):
 - Internally invoiced goods and services
- Indirect costs (Article 6.2E)

4.4.2. Details about the nature of costs to submit

Here is a non-exhaustive example of the level of detail expected in the course of a sound financial management:

[SENSITIVE]

According to the procedures and information to be provided to the EC, it is mandatory for the Consortium to deliver the Financial Statement per reporting period in due time to allow the Project Officer the acceptance of costs declared as eligible costs of the project.

4.4.3. Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS)

In accordance with the article 21 of the GA, certificate on the financial statements' for each beneficiary are compulsory, if it requests a total contribution of EUR 430,000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices (see Article 6.2, Point 4.3 of the Data Sheet of the GA).

The model of a CFS is compulsory and it should be drawn up in accordance with Annex 4 of GA. Please ask your auditors to follow strictly the model requested by the EC.

A CFS covering costs declared shall be delivered at the end of the project.

Without prejudice to the paragraph above, the EC may request, on the basis of an analysis of risks, the submission of a certificate on financial statements from any beneficiary at any time until the agreement completion date.

4.4.4. Financial documentation to be kept- supporting documents of costs claimed

According to article 20.1 and Point 6 of the Data Sheet of GA, all beneficiaries have to keep LET'S CARE supporting documentation up to 5 years after payment of the balance, in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible.

According to the IAP (Indicative Audit Programme) from Horizon Europe, in case of an audit (Article 25 of the GA), the following documents needed by the financial auditor will be requested from the participant, as appropriate:

[SENSITIVE]

5. Project Management

5.1. Governance Structure

The project management structure is shown in the following scheme:

[SENSITIVE]

The organizational structure of the Consortium shall comprise the following Management Bodies:

[SENSITIVE]

The complete description of the Consortium bodies (role, composition and meetings) is available on the CA of the project (Section 6).

5.2. Risk management

The GenA will identify and monitor, during project implementation, internal and external risks as well as any other issues that might affect the Project progress towards its objectives, in order to carry out mitigation actions as early as possible. Risks and contingency plans have been identified in DoA (Part A, List of critical risks). Each Partner has the responsibility to report immediately to their respective WP Leader and to the PC, any risky situation that may arise and may affect the project objectives or their successful completion.

Any change in time schedule of deliverables or in the allocated budget must be reported to the corresponding WP Leader or to the PC.

In case of problems or delays, the WP leader will be consulted, and he/she may install task forces to take the necessary actions.

In case no resolution is reached, the GenA will be consulted and will establish mitigation plans to reduce the impact of risk occurring.

5.3. Quality management plan

In order to ensure the quality of the project management, special focus should be made on the information flow and management, on the reporting, as well as on the document's elaboration and review.

The sections 4 and 6 of this Quality Management Plan updated deal with these aspects, particularly:

- Information Management: documentation management and templates (including deliverables management) and meetings management are described in the Section 6 of this document.
- Meetings management (detailed information in Section 6.1.1).
- Document management (detailed information in Section 6.2.1).
- Technical and administrative information flow (detailed information in Section 6.2.2 and 6.2.3).
- Templates (detailed information in Section 6.2.4).
- Review and submission of deliverables (detailed information in Section 6.2.5).
- Project reporting: deadlines and information flows, responsibilities and contents are described in the section 4 of this document.
- Periodic reporting (detailed information in Section 4.1).
- Continuous reporting (detailed information in Section 4.2).
- Interim progress reporting (detailed information in Section 4.2.2).

Additionally, a set of key performance indicators (KPIs) have been selected based on the four main measurement typologies used in project management: timeline, budget, quality and effectiveness. Detailed information concerning the KPIs is shown in section 6.1.3.

6. Work Information Management

To ensure congruence between project outputs and requirements, a robust Quality Assurance approach has been established, comprising Quality Planning and Quality Control and Monitoring. This framework aims to facilitate the execution of activities in accordance with established planning and standards.

6.1. Quality Planning

6.1.1. Meetings

In order to assure an adequate execution and monitoring of the project, the following meetings have been planned:

[SENSITIVE]

The following sections include the most relevant considerations included in the CA regarding the Project Management Board and Technical Committee meetings.

[SENSITIVE]

6.1.2. Periodic reporting

The periodic reporting is the procedure used by the EC to assess and follow-up the financed RIAs and IAs in Horizon Europe. Therefore, it is of utmost importance, as it conditions in a very direct way the good image and good assessment of the project by the EC.

It is important to remark that periodic reporting is a responsibility of the whole Consortium, and every partner has to be involved in it. The PC is the responsible for gathering the information and reports from the different partners and consolidating it before sending it to the EC.

According to the Article 21 Point 4.2 of the Data Sheet of the GA, the LET'S CARE project is divided into 3 reporting periods (RP):

- RP1: from month 1 to month 12 → 1st Periodic report.
- RP2: from month 13 to month 27 → 2nd Periodic report.
- RP3: from month 38 to month 48 → 3rd Periodic report.

Thus, 3 periodic reports and a final report will be submitted to the EC within 60 days following the end of each RP. These reports will make up by a periodic (or final) technical report and a periodic (or final) financial report.

In order to receive the updated information about the progress of the project, each partner will also report interim progress reports to the PC on month 36 (D7.4). This covers technical progress, results, deliverables and compliance with the WP schedule, as well as the monitoring and updating of the identified risks. Progress of the task is reported in terms of percentage of completion and estimated time to completion, deviations from agreed time scales and corrective actions. The PC summarises overall project progress, updating planning charts and the efforts dedicated. The process of information gathering starts one month before the internal deadlines.

All templates are shared with the consortium in due time.

6.1.3. Performance indicators reporting

Tracking key performance indicators (KPIs) are critical during the project as an effective project management measure. It is considered difficult to see how the project is progressing toward the fulfilment of the overall goals and milestones. For this reason, a set of KPIs have been selected based on the four main measurement typologies used in project management: timeline, budget, quality, and effectiveness. Table below gathers a general description about them, and they will be tracked during the project progress.

[SENSITIVE]

The evolution of the KPIs will be updated during the submission of the interim reports, the periodic reports and the final report.

6.1.4. Decision making mechanism

Decisions have to be made always at the right decision level. In this sense, the roles and responsibilities of each Consortium body are defined in the project CA. Overall, the Project Coordinator has the ultimate responsibility for ensuring the quality standards, with the assistance of the Project Office for the continuous supervision and monitoring. WP leaders are responsible for the correct implementation and reporting to the superior level. The external supervision and peer-review of the REA at periodic assessments will confirm the project's compliance with the funding objectives, help to identify areas for improvement, and provide recommendation and suggestions of corrective actions to address any quality improvement needed in the project's implementation. These roles and responsibilities collectively contribute to the effective implementation of Quality Management practices within the project, fostering a culture of quality and continuous improvement.

6.1.5. Veto rights

The veto rights can be exercised by each of the individual members according to the CA.

6.2. Quality Control and monitoring

6.2.1. Document management and internal communication

The management procedures have to guarantee that the documents in the project are produced, updated, distributed, and stored correctly and efficiently. The LET'S CARE internal management, will follow a structured framework for communication throughout the life of the project. This framework remains adaptable to evolving communication needs. The Project Office (PO), and ultimately the Project Coordinator (PC), assume a pivotal and proactive role in ensuring effective communication and smooth execution of the workplan. Internal communication primarily pertains to the processes and tools employed among project partners.

The official documentation for LET'S CARE project will be accessible through its project repository. The partners will use an internal cloud in cloud.europole.org as the primary shared repository that enables an open-source system available for free to all partners. The system allows simultaneous editing of different file formats, compatible with Microsoft office, as well as sharing files with different levels of authorised members from a wider group. The system also permits offline synchronization, and to set up online meetings linked to calendars.

The intranet organization is primarily managed by the Project Office, and Task Leaders are in charge of overseeing and managing the technical information and files necessary for their related implementation. A Consortium contact list has been set up serving as the primary point of reference. This list will be regularly updated by the Project Office to reflect any personnel changes within the partner organizations, ensuring accuracy and accessibility of contact information.

This advanced tool has been chosen to guarantee the security and capacity requirements of the documents to be used in the project. The repository will have different permission levels depending on the users and the users are allowed to edit, upload and download documents according to the permissions granted in each library or folder.

6.2.2. Technical information Flow Chart

[SENSITIVE]

6.2.3. Administrative Information Flow

[SENSITIVE]

6.2.4. Templates

All the official documents of LET'S CARE (presentations, deliverables, external communication, meeting minutes, etc.) must use the templates which will be available on the project repository.

The project logo and the EU flag including this reference "*Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (Nº 101059425)*" must also be included in all the documents related to the project.

The templates could suffer modifications during the project duration, so it is recommended to download the templates each time an official LET'S CARE document is going to be generated.

All reports and deliverables shall be submitted in English.

This applies to all beneficiaries of LET'S CARE.

6.2.5. Review and submission of deliverables

All the deliverables must be finalized and submitted within the deadlines defined in Annex 1 to the GA. Please see Section 4.2.1 of this document.

All deliverables shall be submitted to the EC, by uploading them to the Funding & Tenders portal.

The Lead beneficiaries of the deliverables are responsible for the elaboration and technical quality of the deliverables. In order to ensure the quality of the delivery to be submitted, the following procedure to review each deliverable has been defined:

[SENSITIVE]

Points to be considered in particular are:

- Does the deliverable fulfil the objectives as set out in the WP description in Annex 1?
- Does the deliverable justify the resources expended as outlined in the progress reports?
- Is the document format correct, including the title page and following the template available?

In case of delay, the WP leader will communicate to the PC the situation and along with the lead partner in charge of the deliverable, they will analyse how to address the problem and they will define a new date for submission of the deliverable as soon as possible. If this happens, the PC will be in charge of informing the EC Project Officer as soon as possible.

7. Financial Contributions and payment issues

Payments to partners are the exclusive task of the PC. According to the GA, the following payments will be made by the EC to the PC:

- 1 pre-financing payment (including a 5% guarantee fund)
- 1 or more interim payments, on the basis of the request(s) for interim payment (see Article 22.3.3 of the GA and CA), and
- 1 payment of the balance, on the basis of the request for payment of the balance (see Article 22.3.4 of the GA and CA).

The information hereinafter has been extracted from the section 7 of the CA (specifically, sections 7. Financial Provisions- and 7.3 Payments):

[SENSITIVE]

8. Project Changes and Potential problem areas

8.1. Project Changes: Amendments to the GA and / or Communication letters to the EC

The basic principle of the project is to carry out the tasks and activities within the time scheduled and resources foreseen as described in the Annex 1 (DoA) to the GA.

Any changes in the status of a beneficiary shall be communicated to the PC as soon as possible. The PC shall resolve queries and advise to beneficiaries. If required, the PC will contact the EC Project Officer responsible and request clarifications and procedures to be followed.

Significant project changes and deviations from the work planned must be dealt with in writing. The participant involved or WP Leader proposing the change should communicate them to the PC, which will forward a written communication to the GenA explaining the reason behind the proposed changes and direct consequences in terms of budget, work programme, etc.

As a general rule, an amendment to the GA is necessary whenever the GA has to be modified. In some cases, the GA gives the parties the possibility to carry out certain modifications without changing the GA. Finally, there are cases where the need for amendment must be assessed carefully.

The amendment request will be forwarded on behalf of the Consortium by the PC to the EC.

Minor changes such as insignificant deviations from time schedule will be dealt within the periodic progress reporting.

8.1.1. Changes requiring amendment to the Grant Agreement

An amendment is necessary when one of the following changes (non-exhaustive list) applies:

- Addition of a new beneficiary
- Addition of an affiliated entity/associated partner
- Beneficiary termination
- Removal of an affiliated entity/associated partner
- Change of coordinator
- Change of the coordinator's bank account for payments
- Changes to Annex 1 (description of the action)
- Change of the starting date, project duration or reporting periods
- Changes to Annex 2 (estimated budget) and Annex 2a, 2b, 2c, 2d, 2e, if necessary

8.1.2. Changes which do not require an amendment: information procedure

- Change in the person in charge of the coordination of the project
- Change of the name of the bank or name of the account holder
- Changes to the due date of a deliverable
- Budget transfers covered by the budget flexibility rule in Article 5.5 of the GA.
- Change of name, address or other legal entity data (of beneficiaries/affiliated entities)
- Universal takeovers

8.1.3. How do I request an amendment?

Amendment requests must be prepared by the requesting party (i.e. the PC or the Commission/Agency) directly in the Funding and Tenders Portal. The request must be unambiguous and complete and submitted in time (i.e. sufficiently in advance to allow proper analysis and preparation before they are due to take effect and — generally — before the end of the action). Requests introduced AFTER the end of the action will be accepted only exceptionally, for very specific (duly substantiated) cases (e.g. change of bank account, change of coordinator to make the payment of the balance).

The PC must ensure that it has the agreement of the consortium (in accordance with the internal decision-making processes, e.g., unanimity, simple or qualified majority, etc. set out in the consortium agreement).

The general steps involved in requesting an amendment are:

1. Prepare your request using the Participant Portal's Grant Management Service:

- The PC launches the amendment request in the Participant Portal Grant Management Service.

- Amend the relevant data in the GA
- Give reasons for (justify) the amendment
- Upload supporting documents
- Make sure the necessary validations are complete (e.g. validation of a new legal entity or bank account)
- Submit your request.

Exception: if a beneficiary's participation is terminated at the initiative of other beneficiaries, the PC must draft a notification to inform the EC of this. The notification must include the request for an amendment.

Requests proposing more than one change to the GA are treated as a package. They cannot be divided into separate requests; the EC accepts or rejects them as an indivisible whole.

Consider submitting changes that require more in-depth reflection (e.g. changes to Annex 1) as a separate request. Requests requiring no discussion (e.g. a change in the coordinator's bank account) can then be dealt with faster.

Please prepare and submit any requests for amendments as soon as possible after you become aware of the need to amend the GA. Amendments take time to be processed and the changes introduced will, in most cases, apply only once the amendment is approved, but not retroactively.

2. The requesting party signs and submits amendments electronically.

- The request (with all its uploaded supporting documents) must be submitted and signed by the PLSIGN of the PC.
- Before it has been accepted or rejected, an amendment request may at any moment be withdrawn. In order to change the amendment request, it must be withdrawn and re-submitted (changes to submitted requests are NOT possible).
- A request containing several changes to the GA will be considered as one (and must either be agreed or rejected by the other party as a whole).

3. The receiving party countersigns the amendments electronically.

- The receiving party must — within 45 days — agree or disagree.
- If the receiving party requests additional information/documents, a new deadline will apply, i.e., 45 days from receiving the additional information/documents.

4. The amendment enters into force and is binding from the moment the receiving party has agreed to it (i.e. signed in the Participant Portal).

5. The amendment will take effect (i.e. the changes to the GA will start to apply) **either:**

- On the day of its entry into force (i.e. day of the last signature of the amendment) or
- On the specific date(s) indicated (and agreed) in the amendment.

The date should normally be after the entry into force of the amendment. In justified cases it may — exceptionally — be before (retroactivity of the amendment). (In some cases, the GA itself provides for retroactivity.)

Detailed instructions about the amendment process can be found in the online manual “Amendments to the Grant Agreement”, available in the following link: [Amendments - Online Manual - Funding Tenders Opportunities \(europa.eu\)](#).

8.2. Potential Problem Areas

The main potential problem for the project is the case that beneficiaries fail to live up to contractual obligations, in particular deliverables due as described in the DoA. Such problems will be dealt with by the GenA, when identified.

Concerning technical problems, different scenarios and problem areas will be described and corrective measures taken when the situation requires during the life span of the project.

Any Partner of the Consortium must inform the WP Leader of any potential inconveniences identified. The WP Leader will duly inform to the TC and the GenA if required.

As already described in section 5.2 (Risk Management), risks and contingency plans have been identified in DoA. The GenA will identify and monitor potential risks as well as other issues that might affect the project to accomplish its goals, to carry out mitigation actions as soon as possible.

All the technical issues must be transmitted from each WP participant to the WP Leader. The WP Leader will be the responsible for dealing with the issue raised and solving it. In the case that the issue cannot be solved, it will be transmitted to the GenA and PC. All relevant issues with an impact on the work and planning of the project will be discussed with the TC and, if it is necessary, with the GenA, without undue delays.

The PC will resolve the issues put up by the WP Leaders or will transmit them to the EC if necessary.